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Review Article

Creatine As a Dietary Supplement for The General Public

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ABSTRACT

Creatine could be a non protein organic amino acid that's either normally delivered within the body or gotten from animal-based nourishments. Inquire about has appeared that creatine admissions is regularly lower than anticipated among different age and se bunches, which is related with certain wellbeing dangers. These things about recommend that creatine supplementation may advantage the common populace by making a difference to anticipate well-being issues and advance superior advancement. Small-scale interventional ponders have reliably illustrated its security and positive impacts on human wellbeing and execution, showing the potential esteem of suggesting creatine more broadly. This paper investigates the reasons for pushing for creatine supplementation on a huge scale and considers the challenges and openings of actualising it for far reaching utilise

INTRODUCTION

Creatine is ostensibly one of the foremost well-known dietary supplements worldwide, with the worldwide creatine advertise evaluated to be \$520 million by 2024 (360 Inquire about Report, 2019). Distinguished as a normal component of skeletal muscle in 1832 by French chemist Michel Eugène Chevreul (Wallimann, 2007), creatine has begun to be explored as a food additive as early as 1912 (Folin & Denis, 1912). The research on creatine skyrocketed within the early 1990s, and nearly 10,000 logical reports up to this point have

assessed its impacts over different spaces of nutrition and biomedicine. Past the shadow of a question, improving exercise performance remains a central field of creatine supplementation (Kreider et al., 2017). In any case, groundbreaking ponders distributed in the past 20 a long time affirmed its advantageous impacts exterior of the athletic arena, counting neuromuscular and cardio metabolic maladies, post-traumatic restoration, and maturing (Kreider & Hefty, 2021). A promising impact of supplemental creatine on

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human well-being and functioning that radiated from small-sized interventional trials perhaps opens a window of opportunity for prescribing creatine to the general public. In this supposition paper, I have sketched out conceivable methods of reasoning for endorsing supplemental creatine ubiquitously and talked about opportunities and challenges for population-wide creatine utilise.

Figure: creatine

2. Creatine turnover: Loss vs. Replacement

Creatine ($C_4H_9N_3O_2$), a constituent of cellular activity that is not a protein, is rather an amino acid. This guanidine compound (also known as acetic acid, methyl guanidine) is synthesised in vertebrates and assists in high-energy phosphate molecules synthesis required for some cellular activity. As a result, 95% of creatine contained within the body is bound with muscle tissues. The remaining 5% is distributed in the brain, liver, both kidneys, and in testes (Persky and Brazeau, 2001). Almost all people take approximately two grams of creatine per day. Such dose is easily divided into two equal parts: half is produced in the liver and kidneys while the other half is received from an omnivorous diet (Brosnan & Brosnan, 2007) (See Figure 1). In contrast, creatine is frequently sustained but when it is left for a long time, it changes to creatinine which is then excreted through kidneys with the average body retention rate of around 1.7%. It follows that the overall handling of creatine is two days (one day counting at the body) (Wyss & Kaddurah-Daouk, 2000). This balance is usually disrupted by the body's inability to create creatine due to lack of creatine-rich food

in one's diet, thus causing damage to a wide variety of energy metabolism conditions. These types of conditions are marked by a marked restorative deficiency of creatine. On top of that, other traits include the presence of a very severe neurological phenotype (Schulze, 2013). The frequency of instance, creatine deficiency syndrome (CDS) refers to a disease caused by a defect in the biosynthesis and receptorial transport of creatine, which is genetically inherited.

3. Creatine consumption in the general population

Creatine can be found in nearly all animal foods like milk, dairy, meat, poultry, fish products, as well as food substances and supplements containing synthetic and purified forms of creatine, predominantly creatine monohydrate (Wu, 2020). Food sources of creatine should provide about 1 g/day, with average consumption being gender and age dependent (Brosnan and Brosnan, 2007). Several recent population studies have, however, reported that dietary creatine intake is inadequate for all age and sex groups. Reports showed that US populations may have a creatine deficiency because average intake was almost 50% lower than recommended amounts. Khan et al. calculated the age and mean daily intake of creatine amounts to 0.54 grams for each participant based on data from the 2012 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. Another research scrutinised dietary creatine consumption in 9254 individuals aged 0-85 years who took part in the NHANES round 2017–2018 (Ostojic, 2021b). Mean creatine intake was recorded to be 1.38 g/day, with approximately 42.8% of the respondents taking less than the recommended daily amount. A survey among 4291 children and adolescents aged 2 to 19 showed a daily intake of 1.07 g (Korovljevic, Stajer, & Ostojic, 2021). Meanwhile, approximately 60% of young participants consumed less than the 1 gram creatine threshold per day, while 17% consumed

zero creatine. The above studies suggest that the population is creatine deficient, with perhaps one in two people consuming too little creatine from food. One explanation for creatine deficiency may include a decrease in the population's meat consumption. Red meat is the most abundant (high creatine) in reduced intake (Neff et al., 2018). It is not clear that a low creatine diet can be fully and easily compensated for by improving endogenous synthesis. Interestingly, preliminary evidence suggests an association between creatine intake and population-level measures of health or growth. Across the data, the prevalence of depression was 42% higher among participants in the lowest creatine intake (0 to 0.26 g/day) compared with participants in the highest quartile of creatine intake (0 to 3.16 g/day) (Bakian et al., 2020). After controlling for demographic and lifestyle variables, adults in the highest quartile of creatine intake still had a 31% lower risk of positive

depression compared with adults in the lowest quartile. Our group found that dietary creatine deficiency is associated with increased health risks in men and women aged 65 years and older, with 2.62% of adults consuming <1 g of creatine per day in the control group and following a different diet. The risk of angina was 1-fold higher and the risk of liver disease was 2.59-fold higher than in adults consuming >1 g of creatine per day (Ostojic and others, etc., unpublished data). In addition, short children and adolescents consume less creatine per day from their normal diet than their peers aged 2–19 years (Korovljevic et al., 2021). For every additional 0.1 g of creatine taken per day, an additional 0.60 cm (simple model) or 0.30 cm (modified model) increase in growth was observed. This research supports the idea that the general population may benefit from dietary creatine for the prevention and control of various health conditions or for rapid growth.

Fig:

(Displays creatine metabolism with daily fluctuations. The data are averaged for men aged 20–39 and 18–29 years, respectively, and constructed on data based on dietary supplementation and natural synthesis/excretion. Green arrows indicate the entry and intake of creatine from meat, both from diet or from internal synthesis, while red arrows indicate its utilization

and natural degradation to byproducts. Key enzymes in the regulation pathway are represented by the following blue circles: (1) L-arginine-glycine amidinyltransferase, EC 2.1.4.1; (2) guanidinoacetate N-methyltransferase, EC 2.1.1.2; and (3) creatine kinase, EC 3.2. Some important abbreviations are GAA, guanidinoacetic acid, and SAM, S-adenosyl-L-methionine. For a better understanding of the color code for the figure.

4. Clinical relevance of creatine supplementation

Creatine supplementation may provide multiple benefits across life stages, medical pathology, and exercise. Here, I focus on the efficacy of creatine in public use and medicine; while there is ample evidence for its use in exercise and sports nutrition elsewhere (Kreider et al., 2017), studies provide a combination of creatine with therapy or other treatments. However, the health benefits of creatine appear to be enhanced when combined with resistance training in clinical and non-clinical settings (Burke et al., 2003; Candow, Kirk, & Duque, 2021; Forbes, Candow, Ferreira, & Souza-Junior, 2021). A positive effect of 5 years of creatine supplementation was observed in patients with choroidal and retinal convolution atrophy, a rare autosomal recessive metabolic disease (Vannas-Sulonen, Sipilää, Vannas, Simell, & Rapola, 1985). Creatine supplementation (0.25 to 0.50 g three times daily) is ineffective in slowing the progression of eye disease. However, muscle atrophy and tubular aggregation are features that often appear early in patients with gyral atrophy, disappear, or improve rapidly, and are found on repeat biopsies when the term creatine supplementation is not available. These preliminary findings are encouraging physicians to slowly but surely try creatine supplementation in many areas, from mild diseases to geriatric diseases, from neuromuscular diseases to cardiometabolic diseases and cancer. For example, creatine supplementation (5 g four times daily for 5 days, then twice daily for 51 days) slightly reduced total cholesterol, low lipoprotein, and triacylglycerol levels in men and women aged 32 to 70 years who had suffered from hyperlipidemia for many years (Earnest, Almada & Mitchell, 1996), suggesting that creatine may alter lipid metabolism in some people. Another intervention trial demonstrated the additional effect of creatine on cardiometabolic profiles in the blood; 5 g of

creatine per day for three weeks was shown to reduce plasma homocysteine levels, which is beneficial for a strict diet in the context of heart disease (Van Bavel, de Moraes, & Tibirica, 2019). The vasoprotective effects of creatine were found in another study in healthy young adults, where creatine supplementation (20 g/day) for one week improved endothelium-dependent microvascular reactivity and increased cutaneous capillary density and recruitment (Moraes, Van Bavel, Moraes & Tibiriç'a, 2014). Additionally, creatine improves long-term cognitive performance in healthy participants (Van Cutsem et al., 2020) and reduces performance in sleep-deprived workers (Cook, Crewther, Kilduff, Drawer, & Gaviglio, 2011), improved intelligence and memory in vegetarians (Benton & Donohoe, 2011) and in people who do not eat meat (Ling, Kritikos, & Tiplady, 2009), as well as slowing neuromuscular fatigue and improving performance and cognition (Gotshalk et al., 2002; Stout et al., 2007; McMorris, Mielcarz, Harris, Swain, & Howard, 2007). In the clinical setting, creatine supplementation helps improve symptoms and endoscopic index of chronic ileitis (Roy & Lee, 2016), leads to bone loss in rheumatoid arthritis (Wilkinson et al., 2016), improves muscle tone in patients with fibromyalgia (Alves et al., 2013), in patients with heart failure (Kueth, Krack, Richartz, & Figulla, 2006) and in patients with Duchennemuscular dystrophy (Felber et al., 2000; Louis et al., 2003; Banerjee et al., 2010), improves the development of CDS (Ganesan, Johnson, Connelly, Eckhardt, & Surtees, 1997; Schulze, Ebinger, Rating, & Mayatepek; Battini et al., 2006; Ndika et al., 2012), and mitochondrial brain lesions (Barisic et al., 2002) contribute to depression resistance to effective measures. On the other hand, short-term or long-term creatine supplementation does not affect cognitive performance in sleep-deprived adolescents (Rawson et al., 2008), potentially

useful in peripheral arterial disease. (Domingues et al., 2021), bone health in postpartum women with and without osteopenia (Lobo et al., 2015; Muag et al., 2020), muscle function in juvenile dermatomyositis (Solis et al., 2016), multiple sclerosis (Malin, Cotugna, & Fang, 2008) and tetraplegia (Kendall, Jacquemin, Frost, & Burns, 2005), childhood systemic lupus erythematosus (Hayashi et al., 2014) and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (Drory & Gross, 2002; Shefner et al., 2004), infants with apnea of prematurity (Bohnhorst et al., 2004), Parkinson's disease (Bender et al., 2006) and improvement is seen in cancer patients (Norman et al., 2006), Huntington's disease (Bender et al., 2005), cystic fibrosis patients (Braegger et al., 2003) or rheumatoid arthritis (Willer, Stucki, Hoppeler, Brühlmann, & Krähenbühl, 2000).

In clinical medicine, consistent results from creatine trials may depend on several factors, including accurate creatine levels and specific diseases that respond (or do not respond) to creatine intervention. Creatine is usually used for a short period of time (<3 months) at different doses (e.g., from 0.25 g creatine to more than 20 g creatine per day). Several studies have shown an anti-inflammatory effect with low doses of creatine generally comparable or even superior to higher doses in terms of efficacy and safety (Vorgerd and Zange, 2007). This requires time-consuming and meticulous research to find the best dosage for creatine. Creatine is added to aqueous solutions and foods in powder or granular form or is dispersed in dosage forms (e.g., tablets, capsules). Creatine monohydrate ($C_4H_{11}N_3O_3$) is almost exclusively used as a drug form of creatine. However, monohydrate formulations may have limited bioavailability, transport, and storage (Ostojic, 2020b), and other creatine mimics should be developed and formulated strictly in medically reviewed diets. Creatine appears to be beneficial for diseases and conditions that impair the body's

ability to synthesize/accumulate creatine, for individuals who do not have sufficient creatine in their diet, and for older individuals with skeletal muscle symptoms. It is important to improve after treatment. Creatine supplementation is negative for neurodegenerative diseases, bone health, and cancer. This may encourage further research on creatine in the general population, perhaps by determining which groups may benefit from creatine and which groups are less well understood.

5. Safety of creatine supplementation

Over the past 30 years, creatine has been studied carefully to identify, quantify, understand, and prevent side effects or adverse events associated with its use in human nutrition and medicine. Most pharmacovigilance studies have shown that creatine supplementation has a good safety profile and that creatine does not pose any health risks, and researchers have shown that at different stages and conditions of life 0.03–0.8 g/kg body weight per day for up to 5 years (for a detailed review, see Balestrino and Adriano, 2019; Antonio et al., 2021). A small initial weight gain (approximately 1–2% of body weight) is a regular result of creatine supplementation (Eckerson, Bull, & Moore, 2008; Deminice et al., 2016; Alme Da, Colombini, & Machado, 2020). This effect is dose-dependent, as lower doses of creatine (e.g., 0.03 g/kg/day) do not cause weight gain or significant changes in body size (Rawson, Stec, Frederickson, & Myers, 2011). Based on good evidence from safety testing, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) recently recognized creatine monohydrate as a safe product (generally recognized as safe (FDA), listing creatine as non-toxic. Foods, under intended use conditions. In a study conducted by the Centers for Food Safety and the Applied Malnutrition Event Reporting System (CAERS), data on foods, drugs, and cosmetics submitted to the FDA reported 30,766 reports of creatine (and various products containing creatine) being

recorded in only 23 reports (0.075%) (CFSAN Adverse Event Reporting System, 2021). This further strengthens the evidence that creatine is not harmful, although individual cases should be monitored and carefully evaluated for possible side effects. Clinical studies have shown that creatine supplementation does not increase the risk of intestinal obstruction, musculoskeletal injury, or renal failure (for a detailed review, see Kreider et al., 2017). Interestingly, creatine appears to be safe when taken regularly in the human diet. For example, US adults who consumed 2.0 g of creatine per day were less likely to develop renal failure compared with US adults who consumed lower amounts of creatine (0.74 (95% CI 0.39 to 1.38)) (Ostojic, 2021b), indicating no significant association between creatine intake and renal dysfunction in the general population. However, patients with renal failure should not receive creatine therapy unless careful consideration of the risk-benefit balance proves it beneficial (Balesrino and Adriano, 2019).

6. Should everybody take creatine?

Creatine is only obtained from meat products (Journal of Functional Foods 83 (2021) 104568). This fact requires a careful interpretation of daily food policy and public health consumption. In particular, many partner organizations and research centers have recently proposed to re-establish the importance of agriculture in order to support the reduction of animal production and meat consumption in order to prevent climate change, improve human health, and promote environmental support (Jarmul, Liew, Haines, & Schielbeek, Schiermeier, 2019; Willett et al., 2019). Although global food competition may decrease and change significantly in the coming years, lower meat consumption will lead to deficiencies of many specific nutrients, including creatine (Ostojic, 2020c). This will allow the public to decide on strategies to provide adequate creatine to increase the nutritional value load in

food, including low-fat diet pills and food supplements. Both strategies are quite reliable because most creatine deficiencies are high and creatine has been shown to be safe and effective in previous studies. However, there are still many issues to be resolved before creatine supplementation can be considered a public health intervention (Figure 2). For example, no dietary guidelines have been established for creatine because creatine is considered nonessential (Institute of Medicine, 2006), but data suggest that creatine may be as important as appropriate dietary intake to begin with (Reeds, 2000; Post, Tsikas, & Bakker, 2018; Wu, 2020). Second, the best way to deliver creatine to the public is unclear. Food supplementation may be a simple and great idea to add creatine and improve the nutritional quality of food. However, food preservation is often done before symptoms of malnutrition appear in most people. For example, ongoing salt iodization programs have achieved global iodine sufficiency and brought iodine deficiency diseases under control (World Health Organization and Food and Agriculture Organization, 2006). This has not yet been determined for creatine, and only preliminary data are currently available on contamination and food. However, we need to make a sound case for making creatine products available and affordable to the public, and to measure the costs of production and sales. Coincidentally, creatine can be commercially produced by various environmentally friendly activities, and the raw materials for this reaction (such as sarcosinate, acetic acid, cyanide, S-Alkylisothiureas) are readily available as simple chemical components (Pischel and Gastner, 2007). Chemical synthetic creatine does not need to be separated from meat extract. Although large-scale creatine production is possible, we are still not sure about the scale required to complete the food additive under the law. In addition, creatine monohydrate may not be stable under certain conditions (such as low pH,

high temperature, aqueous solution), which requires further modification of solid food production and permitting and the invention of elasticity. Meat-free foods or other foods designed for people’s special dietary needs, mass protection, and regulation by government regulations (Ostojic, 2020c). As a first step, creatine-fortified foods could be developed and studied for various high-risk groups, such as the elderly and the malnourished, vegans, and vegetarians. This failure action plan (i.e., one that could be supported) and additional services could be well

received and shorten the time period during which the idea would be wrongly criticized. The public opinion is that an international network of nutritionists and regulators should come together to make the case for creatine, perhaps using a similar roadmap for choline to create another endogenous compound, once thought to be unimportant but eventually deemed essential. National Academy of Medicine (National Academy of Medicine, National Academy of Medicine 1998).

Fig. 2. Advantages (green) and open questions (orange) for creatine use in the general population. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article) It is urgently necessary to collect more information on the current dietary intake of creatine in different age groups and to investigate the consequences of creatine deficiency and excess, and then to choose creatine testing and factors affecting these regulations. In addition, we need to better understand the public health and global disease burden of creatine dystrophy, evaluate the role of creatine supplementation in the treatment of creatine dystrophy, and clarify the content of creatine supplements, specific food vehicles and their use.

Sustainable supplementation/food supplementation programs, at least among the affected groups.

CONCLUSIONS

After over 100 years of scientific research into creatine, it’s time to consider this simple yet wonderful nutrient, not just another beauty supplement. Evidence suggests that inadequate dietary creatine intake cannot be fully compensated for by internal synthesis, suggesting that creatine is an essential amino acid derivative for humans. The health benefits associated with low creatine intake found in ecological studies provide additional basis for creatine value, and the creatine-deficient population, see our creatine distribution strategy for the public. But there’s still

a long way to go before creatine becomes a dietary supplement for everyone. Hopefully, this journey will transcend science and medicine, encouraging doctors to see creatine as an essential part of health in the twentieth century.

Ethical statement

This is a review paper, which doesn't include animal or human experiments

Declaration of Competing Interest

Studies S.M.O. is a member of the Scientific Committee on Creatine in Health and Medicine (AlzChem LLC). S.M.O. holds the European Patent Office patent "Liquid creatine-based sports supplement" (WO2019150323 A1) and the current patent application "Synergy Creatine" (GB2012773.4) with the UK Intellectual Property Office. S.M.O. has worked as a spokesperson for Abbott Nutrition, consultant for Adriatic and IMLEK Allied Beverages, member of the Board of Directors of the Faculty of Medicine at the University of Novi Sad and has received research funding from the Serbian Education, Science and Creatine from the Ministry of Technological Development, the State Agency for Higher Education and Scientific Research, AlzChem GmbH, KW Pfannenschmidt GmbH, ThermoLife International LLC and Monster Energy Company. S.M.O. is an employee of the University of Novi Sad, does not own any stocks and is not involved in any organization. The funders were not responsible for the study collection, analysis, or interpretation of the data.

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